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gender equality to unlock
research potential

D5.1 Guidelines on monitoring and evaluation

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¹ PU= Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

CE	Consulta Europe
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
DB	Database
EC	European Commission
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
EU	European Union
FRCT	Fundo Regional para a Cienciaa e Tecnologia
GE	Gender Equality
GEA	Gender Equality Audit
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GOBCAN	Gobierno de Canarias
IJS	Institut Jozef Stefan
M	Month
M&E	Monitoring & Evaluation
NGO	Non-governmental organization
R&D+I	Research, Development and Innovation
RFO	Research Funding Organization
RPO	Research Performing Organization
SAS	Slovak Academy of Sciences
UB	Universitatea din Bucuresti
UJK	Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego w Kielcach
ULPGC	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
URAK	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
WP	Work Package
UVSK SAV	Ustav Vyskumu Socialnej Komunikacie Slovenskej Akademie Vied

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

This Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) Guide presents key guidance on strategies for monitoring Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) implementation and evaluating progress made in gender-aware structural changes in Athena RPOs and RFOs.

Athena Project is focused on generation a sustainable cultural and institutional change through the development and implementation of eight self-tailored Gender Equality Plans, which in turns will allow to unlock the research potential of the partnering organizations.

The guide is planned to support the implementation of Athena Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and provides guidance on how to develop and implement an M&E framework for gender equality measurement; provides M&E indicators for each of the eight GEP, and advice on how to design and implement M&E system and processes.

It is intended to be used alongside the Athena GEPs action plans, the knowledge gained in WP2, guidelines provided in WP 4 and other Athena documents, linking to further useful resources as needed.

Guideline aims to ensure a coherent approach among all Athena Partners for impartially monitoring and evaluating the progress made in reducing gender inequality in Athena Organizations.

1.2 Document structure

This deliverable describes:

1. Developing an Athena Monitoring and Evaluation system – key guidelines
 - 1.1. Scope and definitions
 - 1.2. Concept and Approach
 - 1.3. Monitoring basic principles and procedures
 - 1.4. Impact and satisfaction measurement process
 - 1.5. Reporting and Dissemination
2. ATEHENA Monitoring and Evaluation Framework of Indicators
3. Guidelines and Timeline
4. Annexes

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2 Developing an Athena Monitoring and Evaluation system

2.1 Scope and definitions

Quality of each project or program means that the product or services meet the intended objectives of the project and have a value to the funding entities and stakeholders and that the target groups can use the product or service as it was originally intended.

Hence, the monitoring and evaluation system is the process for ensuring that all activities necessary to design, plan and implement a project are effective and efficient with respect to the purpose of the objective and performance.

The assessment's structure and procedures shall be adequate to the objectives and complexity of the project. Key components of the monitoring and evaluation are outputs and processes, which must respond to the expected quality standards and to stakeholders' expectations.

In this concept the monitoring and evaluation instruments are firstly to be seen as tools supporting effective actions and creating accountability. Secondly, by providing indicators against which actions can be assessed and resources allocated, they also enhance knowledge of ongoing changes.

Box 1.

Monitoring: *is systematic process of collecting, analysing and using information to track a programme's progress toward reaching its objectives and to guide management decisions. Monitoring usually focuses on processes, such as when and where activities occur, who deliver them and how many people or entities they reach.*

Evaluation: *is the systematic assesment of an activity, project, programme, strategy, policy, topic, operational area or institutions' performance. Evaluation focuses on expected and achieved accomplishments, examining the results chain (inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes and impacts). Processes, contextual factors and causality, in order to understand achievements or lack of achievements.*

Sources: [Programming Essentials Monitoring&Evaluation](#) UNWOMEN Virtual Knowledge Centre to End Violence against Women and Girls

Evaluation defined by European Commission² is a critical, evidence-based judgment of **whether an intervention has met the needs it aimed to satisfy and actually achieved its expected effects.**

It goes beyond an assessment of whether something happened or not, and looks at causality – whether the action taken by a given party altered behaviours and led to the expected changes and/or any other unintended or unexpected changes.

Evaluation is a process that seeks to determine as systematically and objectively as possible the **relevance, usefulness, effectiveness and impact** of an ongoing or completed project in the light of its objectives and accomplishments.

Besides, this is a major part of learning, and can provide a wealth of useful information on the outcomes of a programme, project or action, and the dynamics of those who undertook the work.

Box 2

M&E system should be an essential part of the management and decision making process and an integral part of every intervention and should be considered across the cycle:

assessment – planning – design - implementation - evaluation

M&E instruments should be viewed as part of the Plan and considered before any intervention takes place.

In Athena Project the methodology for impartially monitoring and evaluation the progress made on gender equality is defined **as formative (accompanying)**, helping the partners to adapt their GEPs, if needed.

Formative evaluation is undertaken early in the development of the program/project/plan to inform the providers and stakeholders about the trends in results, whether the goals of the program are likely to be fulfilled, and to identify the barriers and facilitators of implementation.

Results of the formative evaluation are then incorporated into the program with the necessary adjustments made to improve action plans implementation.

² European Commission, *Evaluation EU Activities*, DG Budget 2005, <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/6ff3c67d-bd1e-4909-8158-01cd57c4375d>

Box 3

Implementation of gender equality measures in RPOs and RFOs are interventions in complex systems as they involve a variety of stakeholders, interact with other processes and strategies and have to become engaged on different organizational levels.

Accompanying evaluations can help to support these complex implementation processes as they provide up to date information and knowledge about the status of implementation processes and enable reflection on actual implementation practices.

This will enable to recognise implementation practices which are not feasible or successful and to identify actors which are inhabiting progress and success. On the other hand it also make evident which implementation practices are achieving their objectives.

Sources: [Genera project](#)

This living character of the assessment concept is a necessary as the implementing Athena RPOs and RFOs will develop their self-tailored Gender Equality Plans, and the monitoring and evaluation concept should be adapted to these plans and concrete actions.

Therefore the overall objective of this accompanying evaluation is **the assesment of the implementation process and the applied practices of the Athena partnering research organisations.**

The Athena M& system aims to:

- **track GEP progress and effectiveness:** M&E can help to identify whether a plan is on track to achieve its intended results or whether adjustments are needed. It can assess the success of an intervention and identify whether interventions work, for whom and why;
- **build a evidence base on what works to bring institutional change in Research for Gender Equality;**
- **help identify the most effective and efficient interventions;**
- **identify and manage resistances that could affect the plans and target groups.**

An important step in developing an M&E system is designing **a theory of change for strategy**, which maps:

- Expected pathways for change in knowledge, attitudes and behaviours related to gender equality;

- How these pathways lead to the desired impact?
- The assumptions made that explain the pathways and processes expected to lead to change.

A methodology for impartially monitoring and evaluating the progress made on gender equality should lead to:

- Assessment of progress made on reducing gender bias in RPOs and RFOs
- Identifying implementation practices in different organizations and their achievements
- Assessment of implemented activities and measures through combining an ex-ante and ex-post perspective
- Assessment of target groups' satisfaction
- Identifying organizational changes, institutional progress & benefits
- Identifying challenges and barriers
- Contributing to the Athena learning environment.

Evaluation in this sense is conceptualized as a learning process which reflects implementation practices against the backdrop of specific cultural and structural context and provides important information for adapting implementation practices.

Inspirations & Sources:

[Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans](#)
[Gender Equality in Academia and Research - GEAR Tool](#)
[GENERA - Gender Equality Network in the European Research Area](#)
[RESPECTWomen: Preventing violence against women](#)

2.2 Concept & Approach

Following the concept of formative evaluation the Athena M&E system will focus on implementation practices in each GEPs implementing organization of the Athena project consortium, where the implementation processes and the applied practices to reach objectives set in the self-tailored GEPs will be analysed.

Besides, the evaluation will be extended to **the institutional progress and structural changes** caused by implemented measures.

The M&E system is concentrated on **three main evaluative questions** which are guiding evaluation structure and process.

The first question focuses on **deficiencies of implementation processes and tries to highlight which practices proved to be successful and which**

challenges and resistances are noticed and how could be resolved. This evaluative question opens up the following more specific questions:

- How do these practices, outputs and achievements reflect and contribute to the structural and cultural change in each organization?
- What kind of implementation practices and approaches can be identified in each organization?
- Have the measures contributed to a higher awareness of different target groups for gender (in) equality?
- Were the implementation practices confronted with resistances?
- What is the background to and what are the reasons for resistances?
- Which practices were successful in overcoming resistances?
- Why was it not possible to overcome resistances?

The second question is focused on the **implementation processes and practices of measures and actions** that is concerned with the assessment of measures and actions implemented and whether they were **successful in achieving their goals**. So this question focuses very much on outputs and achievements. The following more specific questions are:

- What actions and measures were implemented in each organization?
- What was their concrete output of these actions? And what kind of achievements can be identified?
- Were the target groups of the different measures and activities reached and adequately addressed?
- Are there any support services in place to facilitate the implementation of measures and activities? Which?

The third evaluative question is concerned with the **sustainability** of measures and actions:

- Where the actions implemented in a sustainable manner?
- Is it foreseen to continue these interventions after the end of the Athena project?
- How are these measures prolonged and made sustainable?

M&E actions are not a separate, independent process that occurs at the end of an activity to measure the level of quality of the output.

It is a continuous process that starts and ends with the project or program and should focus on improving stakeholders' satisfaction and requirements.

Following this methodology an Athena on-going monitoring **will be put in place in parallel with the implementation of the GEP under WP4**.

All GEPs measures and actions will be regularly monitored by established logic model with appropriate qualitative and quantitative implementation-oriented indicators that are adapted to the purpose of each GEPs actions (see *ATHENA Monitoring and Evaluation System - Framework of Indicators*).

On the other hand evaluation will focus on outcomes, achievements and benefits of the implementation process in each organization and level. The short and – medium term benefits of the implementation process will be identified during the preparing GEPs action plan and framework of indicators.

The evaluation design does not include a long term impact analysis. As the implementation of gender equality measures in each organisation will not start right at the beginning of the project the measures will run for two and a half year. This will not be sufficient to measure long term outcomes or impacts. Nevertheless the long-term indicators will be defined which will allow to collect data to be able to measure those outcomes within each institution even after the runtime of Athena has ended.

A final evaluation will compare the status quo before (ex-ante) and after (ex-post) the interventions have taken place. This will allow to determine the outputs and achievements of Athena's GEPs measures and activities.

Final evaluation will be based on:

- A combined analysis of quantitative and qualitative results
- Significant achievements and failures assessment
- Quality satisfaction survey of the staff.

This will facilitate the learning environment within the ATHENA project consortium but will also lead to a better understanding of implementation processes and practices and will therefore be of considerable value for other research organizations which are striving to implement GEPs and promote gender equality.

Methodology, Instruments and Sources

Logic Model

To ensure coherence of Athena Gender Equality Plans with key GE areas defined in the EU GEP Guideline, and with Athena projects activities logic models will be set up for each eight Athena participating organization aiming to delineate the individual goals, resources and activities of the implemented measures.

The measures and activities of each GEPs as well as developed matrixes of indicators are incorporated into a logic model to display the links between inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes and five GE main areas. (see *ATHENA Monitoring*

and Evaluation System - Framework of Indicators). The common templates for developing logic model of each GEP is developed by UJK with assistance of CNR (see Annex I).

Desk research

The purpose of the desk research in the Athena evaluation is to systematically collect information from various official documents on gender equality, human resource development and overall strategic objectives of each participating organisations.

Quality satisfaction survey of the staff

The main goal of survey will be data collection on satisfaction, success factors and barriers. The survey will be used also to get a first overview of gender equality policies and strategies in each participating organization. This should give first insight in the different development stages of gender equality policies and practices. It is foreseen for the implementation analysis at the end of the project.

Secondary data sources&analysis

Data on the defined quantitative and qualitative indicators will be collected. The data will be used in an aggregated form.

GEPVISION tool and Internal monitoring reports

To get a better overview on the status quo of implementation activities Athena partners will provide two internal reports each year starting from M24 and 1 final evaluation report. These reports will summarize the main activities and events during the one year of GEP implementation and will be used to further tailored and modified the GEPs according the monitoring results.

Parallel with implementing Athena GEPs (within task 4.4.) the supporting on-line tool for monitoring assessment will be provided. GEPVISION platform will facilitate data collection from the GEPs and, its monitoring and visualization of indicators, providing the evidence of changes in the different organizations. This tool will be configured by CNR according to the defined indicators framework and will be interfaced with the Web based community platform.

In final assessment categories and dimension for content analysis will be developed on the basis of the evaluative questions and of the final set of indicators but will be also open to topics and dimensions emerging during the monitoring analysis. These categories will be developed for the analysis of the ex-ante status qua and also applied to the ex-post analysis.

2.3 Monitoring basic principles and procedures

The overall aim is the assessment of the implementation processes and the related practices of each implementation team within each organization.

The general aim of this process is that the project follows the described GEPs action plans.

In this step it will be investigated whether the way a measure is implemented corresponds to the respective goals and objectives, which factors promote or constrain its implementation, which practices contribute to successfully implemented measures and actions, what benefits they might provide for the participating universities and the influence they may have on other (local, regional or national) universities and scientific institutions.

The main activities under this stage refer to:

- monitoring of the GEPs action plan and an effective on-time delivery of the outputs;
- comparing actual GEP's performance against the action plan;
- identifying, analyzing, tracking, and monitoring existing (and new) resistances;
- maintaining an accurate, timely information base concerning the GEPs outputs;
- monitoring implementation of approved changes as they will occur;
- providing appropriate reporting on the progress and status.

Monitoring should take into account a variety of information from variety of different sources gathered using the techniques of Internal monitoring and technical reporting.

It should give the answer to the questions:

- What actions and measures were implemented in each Athena organization?
- How were they implemented?
- How does the completion of activities compare with the planned timeline?
- Have the activities completed to date had required results? What kind of achievements can be identified?
- Were the target groups of the different measures and activities reached and adequately addressed?
- Where there any additional issues encountered during the implementation? What could have been improved about the implementation process?
- Are the measures on track to reach their objectives as envisaged?

Additionally, the internal monitoring have to provide the information of deviation during the project implementation.

- Was the implementation confronted with resistances? If so, by whom?
- What is the background to and what are the reasons for resistances?
- Which practices were successful in overcoming resistances?
- What kind of strategies and argumentations were helpful to overcome those barriers and/or resistances?
- Why was it not possible to overcome resistances?
- What practices are applied to enable sustainability?

The main elements monitored by this process refer **to the activities/measures, outputs/outcomes indicators** and **timeline** defined in GEP action plans leading to the specific objectives of each self-tailored Plan.

Monitoring is carried out by assessing both the work completed to date, and the planned activity. Effectively this means through assessment against the **action plan and the framework of Indicators for each self-tailored Gender Equality Plan**.

2 internal monitoring reports in M24 and M36 at the organizational level will be produced and will be used to assess the progress made and the potential improvement to be done.

Additional monitoring data analysis in final report is foreseen.

The aim of the reporting is to provide sufficiently detailed information to check the advancement of the in light of its objectives and timetable. The results will indeed help the partner organizations tailor and modify their GEPs to perform better achievements (see *Reporting and Dissemination*).

For monitoring processes following procedures will be provided:

- (1) Each Athena partner implementing GEP must provide quantitative and qualitative data according to their self-tailored GEPs action plan.
- (2) The common template for defining outputs and outcomes indicators was provided and distributed among the partners by UJK in M12 according to the logic model (see Annex I).
- (3) Each institution implementing GEPs and developing its action plans will provide the quantitative and qualitative indicators using this template.
- (4) Then, after the preparation of the logical matrix of each GEPs, the indicators are analysed by the gender experts of UJK and the CNR team and the final version is delivered to the GEPVISION platform. The GEPVISION tool is configured by CNR.

(5) In parallel to the implementation of the GEPs, data of achieved outputs and outcomes are systematically collected on the GEPVISION platform when the respective action is completed.

(6) In M24 and M36 Athena partnering organizations prepare their internal monitoring reports on achieved results based on the collected data on qualitative and quantitative indicators using a template prepared by UJK and instruments enabled by GEPVISION tool.

UJK as a lead partner responsible for monitoring report (task 5.3.) will prepare **the common template for monitoring reporting**. Then all Athena partner organisations implementing GEPs prepare their reports on individual action plan.

The results should indeed help the partner organizations tailor and modify their GEPs to perform better results

It is therefore recommended that each GEP implementing partner designates responsible entities/bodies for data collection and reporting.

Responsible unit/persons should conduct regular reviews of key project outputs and reports with the GEPI Committee and RFOs or RPOs management bodies, and will discuss the reports and agree on necessary corrections or improvements where required.

During the runtime of the Athena project and GEP implementation processes, Partners are encouraged to upload systematically the data on completed actions on the GEPVISION platform.

Reports should be distributed/disseminated among GEPIs Committee members and other stakeholders, if needed.

On one side, these reports aim to help GEPI Committees and the implementing organisations to understand the progress made thanks to the implementation of the GEPs. On the other side, if needed, they should identify the remaining challenges and barriers and provide tailored solutions to address them properly and change the GEP accordingly.

2.4 Impact and satisfaction measurement process

Evaluation is an essential part of the management and decision making process. Besides, this is a major part of learning, that can provide a wealth of useful information on the outcomes of a project or action, and the dynamics of those who undertook the work.

The aim of the evaluation is to assess the overall performance of Athena Gender Equality Plans practices, activities and measures implemented in the course of

the Athena project, their success in relation to its specified objectives, and how they interact and link with existing measures and activities, in particular those that address gender mainstreaming related issues.

The main objective of the evaluation research is to demonstrate to which extent the implementation of GEPs contribute to unlock the research potential of partnering RPOs and RFOs. In particular through:

- increasing the participation of women in research and innovation and improvement of their careers prospects;
- improvement of gender balance in decision-making in research organisations;
- inclusion where relevant, of the gender dimension in research content and increase in the quality and societal relevance of produced knowledge, technologies and innovations.

This analysis will assess the outputs and achievements of implemented measures and actions as well as of the whole Athena project within each implementing organization. It therefore tries to evaluate the changes within each organization that can be attributed to a specific Athena measure and activity. This concept based on two pillars:

(1) each measure and activity that has been implemented in the course of the Athena project will be analysed in terms of objectives, design, coherence, implementation and outputs and achievements on the basis of available data and information.

(2) the whole set of measures will be analysed how it addresses different weaknesses and bottlenecks of gender equality in each organization and how it fits to the organizational context and to the measures already in place.

An impact evaluation will compare the ex-ante status and ex-post perspectives after the interventions have taken place. In contrast to an outcome and impact assessment this analysis looks at medium term results.

The ex-post evaluation should give the more integrated and meaningful picture of overall project achievements concerning all the aspects of the project. The evaluation reports should comprise the descriptive analysis and quantitative information to support subsequent planning and operations.

The evaluation shall answer the questions: Why there is success or failure and what has been learned to improve future action and/or sustainability of the project? That rise more specific questions:

- Which outputs and achievements did the implemented intervention produce?
- Do these contribute to structural and organizational changes?

- Did it unlock the research potential of Athena RPOs and RFOs? In which way?
- Have the Athena GEPs measures contributed to a higher awareness of different target groups for gender (in) equality?
- How was it possible to achieve these outputs?
- Are the Athena GEPs actions implemented in a sustainable way?
- Is it foreseen to continue these interventions after the end of the Athena project?
- How are these measures prolonged and made sustainable?
- Did Athena enable learning effects between Athena partners on the one hand and other involved personnel of participating research organizations?

Other evaluation questions could be added, as appropriate starting the evaluation research processes.

As common instruments of ex-post evaluation will be distributed at the end of Athena project the questions will be additionally clarified by key project stakeholders and Athena partnering organisations.

Evaluation activities will follow the standards of evaluation process. Therefore, steps involved in evaluation procedures will include the following:

1. Design and plan the evaluation: clarifying the specific subject and goals, intended outcomes of the evaluation and procedures including timeframes and indicators; determining the questions to answer; identifying stakeholders, sources of data and material to be collected and analysed; identifying data collection methods, approaches and techniques, providing for the accessibility of interviews and/or the survey.

2. Gather information

3. Analyze collected data

4. Produce Report with conclusions responding to the outcomes which the evaluation was originally seeking.

According to the evaluation standards, to ensure a consistent approach to quality assessment of evaluation reports, an ex-post evaluation should be assessed on the basis of following criteria:

Effectiveness. To what extent did the implemented activities cause the observed changes? To what extent do the observed results correspond to the objectives? Have applied activities and their delivery methods been effective? Are there any aspects that could have been done differently?

Efficiency. What factors influenced the achievements observed? What aspects of the participatory elements of the GEPs could be done differently next time to cut costs while still delivering achievements? Were the size, scale and approach taken for each need?

Impact. What is the added value of GEPs implementation? What range of outcomes (intended and unintended) has each GEP contributed to – taking into account of each of social, economic, environmental and cultural considerations? Were GEPs impacting positively on key target groups?

Sustainability. Is there evidence that the initiative is likely to grow – scaling up and out – beyond the Athena project life? To what extent did the initiative deliver against the needs of key stakeholders?

Other evaluation criteria may be added, as appropriate.

Instruments and sources

The ultimate assessment for quality are target groups, and represents how close the outputs and achievements come to meeting the target groups requirements and expectations.

The Athena GEPs outputs and achievements analysis will be based on:

(1) Desk research and data analysis on the common database of quantitative and qualitative indicators developed in M16 referring to the standards and the targets previously developed in WP4

(2) Internal Monitoring Reports analysis

(3) On-line satisfaction survey to assess the qualitative satisfaction of the staff

Specific steps of evaluation process and special evaluation satisfaction questionnaires will be created in M43 by UJK.

As it was mentioned, the results will be compared to the organisation's situation at the beginning of the project described in the Gender Equality Report in WP2.

2.5 Reporting and Dissemination

According to the ATHENA project **monitoring reports are foreseen in moths 24 and 36, in month 48 the final evaluation report** will be produced that will include the monitoring data, too.

The main purpose of reporting is providing information to ensure the implementation of the GEPs, to assist Project Partners with the implementation of GEPs.

The internal reports should accurately reflect project partner progress on the various activities for which they have responsibility according to their GEPs action plans during the reporting period, highlighting any key issues and providing justification for any deviations from the description of the plans.

Important issue in terms of standards and evaluation culture, is **the use of knowledge obtained from monitoring and evaluation research processes**. In other words:

- Whether and to what extent the recommendations of the conducted evaluation research influence the change of the direction of organisations?
- Does the examined institution treat the evaluation analysis as a source of knowledge and a result-based management tool?

It is highly recommended **to use the monitoring and evaluation reports for evidence-based management** in each Athena RFOs and RPOs that should **result in sustainability and quality assurance of Athena Gender Equality Plans**.

Reporting and Dissemination procedures & tips

(1) All reports should be in English but as the purpose of the reports is to assist in the GEPs implementation process, it is recommended the reports to be translated into the national languages.

(2) UJK as the lead partner of task 5.3. is responsible for internal reporting. But the **internal reports should be preceded by reports from each eight Athena partnering organization** that implements **GEP reflecting their progress, and other additional information**.

(3) **The templates of monitoring reports** and additional common guidelines will be prepared by the team of UJK and distributed in M22, M34 and M44.

(4) All Athena organizations implementing GEPs provide internal monitoring reports in M24, M36 and M48.

(5) **The final impact report** will be produced in M48 that **will summarize the outcomes and the results achieved in each organization**. Furthermore, it **will draw conclusion and recommendations** for a better implementation of gender

equality interventions in future. This report will highlight the improvement gained in terms of gender equality and research thanks to the implementation of the GEPs.

(6) The final evaluation report will be developed and submitted to peer review for publication.

(7) Internal monitoring results should be disseminated among GEPI Committee, management bodies, authorities of each Athena partnering organization, and defined stakeholders groups if needed.

(8) Final evaluation report will be submitted for publication, it will be public and will be disseminated among wider audience.

3 ATHENA Monitoring and Evaluation System - Framework of Indicators

Athena Monitoring and Evaluation System is based on the Horizon Europe Guidelines on Gender Equality Plans and available resources analysing the topic of gender equality in Innovation and Higher Education Institutions.

It also corresponds with specific Gender Equality Plans designed by each of the consortium Partners and Gender Equality Audit Indicators Handbook delivered within the Athena Project in 2021.

Monitoring and evaluation processes are performed within specific socio-cultural and economic context. In order for the objectives to be achieved and outcomes to be produced a good understanding of how specific actions, outputs and their indicators relate to current circumstances is indispensable. Currently, one of the key factors shaping our reality is COVID-19. It's impact on gender equality has been thoroughly assessed with special focus on telework and the gender digital divide or impact on the unpaid care burden and living conditions of working parents³. Therefore in order for the M&E system to be relevant it has to take into account the COVID-19 reality.

The M&E System follows with the concept of intervention logic and reflects 5 intervention areas identified in the Horizon Europe Guidelines on Gender Equality Plans:

³ Gender equality and the socio-economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, EIGE 2021 <https://eige.europa.eu/publications/gender-equality-and-socio-economic-impact-covid-19-pandemic>

1. Work-life balance and organizational culture
2. Gender balance in leadership and decision making
3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
4. Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content
5. Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment

Each area is described according to the following logic of intervention:

Figure 1. Logic of Intervention

First the objectives are set, followed by the activities and outputs which lead to the envisioned outcome.

Objectives and outcomes are represented both in an overarching way presenting general goals and impact, as well as by specific objectives and outcomes identified in each Gender Equality Plan of Athena Partners. Outputs are based solely on specific actions indicated in the GEPs.

Outputs and Outcomes are accompanied by indicators measuring the progress at the level of specific actions as well as overall impact. The indicators of outcomes follow the same logic as objectives being both general ones and specific, based on each GEP.

The Monitoring and Evaluation System refers to the 5 intervention areas. The implementation of the Gender Equality Plans requires a separate system designed for each institution.

3.1 Work-life balance and organisational culture

Description of the area of intervention: Work-life balance is relevant for both women and men and involves ensuring that all staff are properly supported to advance their career alongside personal responsibilities that they may hold outside of the workplace, including caring responsibility. According to the European Institute for Gender Equality, work-life balance concerns not only domestic tasks and caring for dependent relatives, but also extracurricular responsibilities or other important life priorities. EIGE indicates that work-life balance covers three areas: paid work, unpaid work (care) and education and training. Within those areas, 6 domains are identified: parental leave policies; caring for children and childcare services; informal care for older persons and persons with disabilities and long-term care services; transport and infrastructure; flexible working arrangements; and lifelong learning.⁴ Work life balance policies can include: parental and caregiver leave policy, flexible working time arrangement, support for caring responsibility including childcare and care for other dependents, workload management, reintegration of staff after career breaks, advice and support on work-life balance.⁵

Objectives⁶:

1. Ensure open and inclusive working and studying environment for everyone regardless of gender and family status.
2. Support employees (academics, administrative staff) and students of all genders in reconciling their work and family life.
3. Provide institutional framework for reconciliation of work and family life.
4. Provide necessary infrastructure for reconciliation of work and family life.

Specific objectives from GEPs⁷:

- Support for employees in the context of maternity/parental leave (before, during and after maternity/parental leave) (SAS GEP)
- Sensitisation of employees to work-life balance issues (SAS GEP)

⁴ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/thematic-focus/work-life-balance>

⁵ Horizon Europe Guidelines on Gender Equality Plans 2021

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ffc06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1>

⁶ ibidem

⁷ Gender Equality Plans of all Athena Partners 2022

- Promoting fathers' involvement in childcare through maternity and parental leave (SAS GEP)
- Kindergarten for the needs of employees of SAS (SAS GEP)
- Development and implementation of principles of flexible working hours (UJK GEP)
- Continue cooperation with the company nursery/preschool (UJK GEP)
- Subsidies from the social insurance fund for children's stay in nurseries and preschools (UJK GEP)
- Providing flexible working arrangements to all employees (JSI GEP)
- Supporting researchers in parental care and care over dependents (JSI GEP)
- Providing flexible working hours (childcare / caretaker remote work etc.) (JSI GEP)
- Developing a career development criteria for young parents (maternity leave, parental leave) (JSI GEP)
- Providing flexibility regarding postdoc (JSI GEP)
- Improve on the currently limited awareness on gender equality and unconscious bias (JSI GEP)
- Gender disaggregated data collection at JSI (JSI GEP)
- Ensuring that the organisation of working time takes into account the need to conciliate professional, family and personal life, particularly for those with family responsibilities (FRCT GEP)
- Ensuring application/adherence to work-life balance solutions (ULPGC GEP)
- Strengthen appropriate work-life balance solutions (ULPGC GEP)
- Promoting work life – personal life balance by establishing a scheme to make working time more flexible for UB employees (UB GEP)
- Promoting the reconciliation of student's educational and care obligations in order to encourage tertiary education for all young people, regardless of family obligations (UB GEP)
- Develop an educational and care structure for pre-school children and schoolchildren of UB staff and students (UB GEP)

- Institutional communication of UB's commitment to work life – personal life balance (UB GEP)
- Ensuring equal opportunities for women and men in the process of studying students and doctoral students, in obtaining scientific degrees, in occupying academic positions and positions in the University administration (URAK GEP)
- Ensuring a better reconciliation of the professional and personal life (URAK GEP)
- Maintain an organizational culture that allows the effective reconciliation of personal and work life for the entire ACIISI staff through support for self-care and care responsibilities towards minors and other dependents (GOBCAN GEP)

Table 1.

Work - life balance and organisational culture: outputs and indicators from Athena GEPs⁸:

Outputs	Indicators of outputs	Gender Equality Plan (institution)
A maternity/parenting plan with recommendations and examples of good practice	Document containing the maternity/parenting plan with recommendations and examples of good practice	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Gender equality training for employees of SAV within the ATHENA project	Number of employees trained	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Presentation of " male caregivers' role models" in the Academy magazine	Number of media publications	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Exploration of the possibilities of establishing a kindergarten in the SAV campus in Patrónka	Implementation strategy to establish a kindergarten in the SAV campus in Patrónka	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Subsidies for children in child care institutions (nurseries	Regulatory act increasing level of subsidies for children in child care institutions (nurseries and	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce

⁸ Gender Equality Plans of Athena Partners 2022

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gender equality to unlock
research potential

and kindergartens)	kindergartens)	
Cooperation with workplace nursery	Number of children at the workplace nursery	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Design and implementation of rules for flexible work arrangements and teleworking	Number of modified/designed procedures	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce

Introduction of flexible working hours at the Jožef Stefan Institute	Amendments to official regulations and contracts with employees	Jožef Institute	Stefan
Childcare support established	Regulatory act increasing level of support for parents in childcare duties	Jožef Institute	Stefan
Measure gender disaggregated HR data	Annual report on disaggregated data as a measure of progress or regression on gender equality issues.	Jožef Institute	Stefan
Goal-oriented work and fixed working hours exemption - Internal organisation of work in a flexible manner through institutional meetings and communications	Internal procedure created and implemented.	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia	
Hybrid work (combination of office-based working with remote days) - Organising the work of each employee with their manager	Internal procedure created and implemented.	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia	
Review and update the internal regulations on leave, leave and holidays of the teaching, research staff and administrative staff	Updated regulations	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	
Review and adapt the application for leave for teaching and research staff to comply with the law and ULPGC's internal regulations	Adapted leave application for teaching and research staff	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	
Organizing an education and care structure for pre-school and young school children of UB's staff and students	Opportunity assesment report and identification of funding sources.	Universitatea din Bucuresti	
Developing regulations on flexible working hours	Adopted regulation on flexible working hours	Universitatea din Bucuresti	

Developing regulations on attendance regime for childcare students, especially young mothers.	Adopted regulation on attendance regime for childcare students, especially young mothers	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Introduce institutional communication on UB's commitment to work-life balance	Number of communications on the UB website and other platforms	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Get current information about the ratio between women and men in teaching, research and administrative activities	Analysed internal documents	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Training of the members of the Ethics Committees on topics related to guaranteeing equality between women and men.	Number of trained members of the Ethics Committee	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Provision of information to parents with small children and large families regarding the possibilities for their stimulation according to national legislation.	Number of trained parents from URAK	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Ensuring equal access when hiring women and men with permanent disabilities usual working and specialized work environment under the National Program for Employment of People with Disabilities, according to Art. 46 and Art. 49 of the Soviet Union and equal access to their education	Number of annually trained and employed women and men with permanent disabilities.	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Provision of opportunities for different forms of employment - hourly, in person, remote environment	Number of participants to these seminars	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev

Provision of a system for informing the university management about the state of equality between women and men in the University.	Number of representatives of the Rector Body, who receive this information	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Continue support for care responsibilities (care for children and other dependents) and parental leave policies	Number of people disaggregated by sex who have requested the permit and have been granted it	Gobierno de Canarias
Maintain flexibility in working hours in accordance with the provisions of the Canarian Civil Service Act	Number of people disaggregated by sex who have requested the permit and have been granted it	Gobierno de Canarias
Reintegration of workers after career interruptions	Number of people disaggregated by sex who have requested the permit and have been granted it	Gobierno de Canarias
Support and advice on Reconciliation of Work Life and Organizational Culture	Number of training days and number of attendees, perhaps they should be included for the entire CECE	Gobierno de Canarias

Outcomes/impact: All students and academic/research staff regardless of their gender and family status have the ability to fulfil their educational and research potential within the HEI or RPO.

Specific outcomes from GEPs⁹:

- Increased access to information and awareness on possibilities for work-life balance for working parents, PhD students with small child/ren, which allows them to perform their academic and research duties (SAS GEP)
- Increased awareness on the possibilities of parental leave to be taken by fathers (SAS GEP)
- Efficient financial support to childcare services for students and academic staff (UJK GEP)
- All students and academic/research staff whose children would like to join child care institution at the University have ability to do so (UJK GEP)

⁹ Gender Equality Plans of Athena Partners 2022

- All employees regardless of gender and family status have access to flexible work arrangements or ability to plan their work time according their needs (UJK GEP)
- All researchers, regardless of gender, have support in case they need to take care of their children or other dependents (JSI GEP)
- Internal legal acts and employment contracts allowing workers to take advantage of the possibility of flexible working hours, remote working including changed career development criteria written in gender sensitive language (JSI GEP)
- All employees, regardless of gender have access to flexible work arrangements (FRCT GEP)
- All employees, regardless of gender have access to flexible work arrangements (UB GEP)
- Equal opportunities for scientific career between women and men (URAK GEP)
- Providing expert capacity on the questions about ensuring equality between women and men (URAK GEP)
- Improved work-life balance of the parents, who are employed at URAK (URAK GEP)
- Building a work environment - access to workplace and administrative service, adaptation of the work environment for people with permanent physical disabilities (URAK GEP)
- Achievement of balance between professional and personal life at the exercise of the rights and obligations of students, the doctoral students, the academic staff and the administrative staff (URAK GEP)
- Maintaining awareness of the University's leadership on the implementation of the equality plan in order to adopt impact measures (URAK GEP)
- All the people who have requested it and meet the legal requirements are granted it (GOBCAN GEP)

Indicators of outcomes¹⁰:

1. Gender pay gap in the organisation by R&D occupations
2. Gender pay gap in the organisation among A-grade academics
3. Proportion of persons employed part-time among researchers
4. Proportion of persons with precarious working contracts among researchers
5. Annual number of researchers on care leave by sex
6. Proportion of people caring for and educating their children or grandchildren, older people and/or people with disabilities, every day
7. The income quintile share ratio (also called the S80/S20 ratio) (a measure of the inequality of income distribution)
8. Age limit extended in calls for female researchers with children under a certain age
9. Mentoring programmes for female employees
10. Gender training for employees
11. Equal access to internal training
12. Specific sabbatical for women scientists
13. Equal access to ability to take an hour or two off during working hours to take care of personal or family matters
14. Possibility to work part-time
15. Maternity institutional policy
16. Paternity institutional policy
17. Child care support (internal kindergarten, on-demand/flexible child care support, etc.)
18. Support/subsidise childcare services
19. Support for re-entry after leave periods
20. Teaching free period after returning from parental leave
21. Family and baby-friendly environment for employees/students
22. Policy on care for elder/dependent family members of employees
23. Flexitime
24. Telework

Specific Indicators of outcomes from GEPs¹¹

- Proportion (%) of women among total number of employed researchers - by age, grade (SAS GEP)
- Number of subsidies granted (UJK GEP)
- Equal access to flexible work arrangements (UJK GEP)
- Equal access to child care institutions (UJK GEP)

¹⁰ Gender Equality Audit Indicators Handbook, Athena Project Deliverable 2021, Gender Equality Index 2019. Work-life balance

¹¹ Gender Equality Plans of Athena Partners 2022

- Annual number and percentage of researchers on maternity/paternity or parental leave in the given year, by gender (JSI GEP)
- Number of researchers working part-time due to childcare, by gender (JSI GEP)
- Number of working days used for care (per researcher) on an annual basis, by gender (JSI GEP)
- Proportion (%) of women among total number of employees in the organisation (all types of contracts (JSI GEP)
- Number of women and men in the administration and support units (JSI GEP)
- Proportion (%) of persons employed part-time among researchers, by gender (JSI GEP)
- Distribution (%) of researchers employed, by gender (JSI GEP)
- Distribution (%) of researchers employed across age groups, by gender; (Age cohorts: <25, 25–34; 35–44; 45–54; 55- 64; 65 and over) (JSI GEP)
- Distribution (%) of researchers in the field of, by gender (JSI GEP)
- Distribution (%) of researchers in the field of Physics and Reactor Engineering, Chemistry, Biology, Materials and Environmental Sciences, Electronics and Information Technology by gender (JSI GEP)
- Number of female and male researchers (Ph.D.) who left JSI in a calendar year, by gender (JSI GEP)
- Number of researchers (Ph.D.) who went abroad for postdoctoral training in a calendar year, by gender (JSI GEP)
- Number of researchers (Ph.D.) who returned from postdoctoral training abroad in a calendar year and (re) employed at JSI, by gender (JSI GEP)
- Number of applicants who applied for national funding within two years after maternity or parental leave (JSI GEP)
- Number of seminars and trainings on gender equality organized at JSI in a calendar year (JSI GEP)
- Number of employees working flexitime and hybrid work (FRCT GEP)
- Number of employees working flexitime (UB GEP)

3.2. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making

Description of the area of intervention: Quantitative representation of women in the leadership positions process translates into qualitative one by allowing female perspective to be included in the decision-making process. It can be achieved by sensitizing leadership on gender related challenges, setting soft or hard quotas for the management positions and making the selection process transparent and inclusive. This area of intervention is often regulated by national policies requiring a certain proportion of women to be represented on the management boards of publicly funded institutions such as Universities or Research Centres. An important aspect to be considered in the area is not only to limit the measures and indicators to purely numeric representation of women in top positions, but also to ensure their actual influence on decisions taken through gender neutral communication, active scouting of women willing to take up leadership positions and ensuring that leadership and decision-making roles are properly recognized in evaluation of research and academic work.¹²

Objectives:

1. Ensure equal access to leadership positions regardless of gender and family status.
2. Provide necessary conditions for all members of the decision making bodies to participate fully in all leadership activities.

Specific objectives from GEPs¹³:

- Sensitisation of employees to the issue of gender equality in management (SAS GEP)
- Increase the proportion of women in the SAS Presidency, in the SAS House Committee and in the leadership of organisations in the 1st and 3rd Divisions of the SAS Sciences (in synergy with HRS4R) (SAS GEP)
- Support for career development with an emphasis on young women scientists (SAS GEP)
- Gender equality training for male and female managers and staff (SAS GEP)
- Continue activities towards equal representation of men and women in the decision-making bodies of UJK (UJK GEP)

¹² Horizon Europe Guidelines on Gender Equality Plans 2021

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ffc06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1>

¹³ Gender Equality Plans of all Athena Partners 2022

- Ensuring equal access to leadership positions for women and men (JSI GEP)
- Ensuring balanced representation of women and men within different boards and committees, within and outside the institute (JSI GEP)
- Introducing and organizing mentoring program, where rapid skill transfer from the mentor to the mentee will be achieved (JSI GEP)
- Promoting training programs as a key element to help women to develop skills in accessing management and decision-making roles (FRCT GEP)
- Ensure equal access to leadership positions regardless of gender and family status (ULPGC GEP)
- Provide necessary conditions for all members of the decision making bodies to participate fully in all leadership activities (ULPGC GEP)
- Increasing institutional commitment to promoting gender equality at the University of Bucharest (UB GEP)
- Promoting the principle of gender equality in the wider community by adhering to the Diversity Charter in Romania (UB GEP)
- Establishing a flexible operational institutional structure for coordinating and monitoring gender equality at UB (UB GEP)
- Improving the process of individual professional performance evaluation of teaching and research staff by introducing specific evaluation criteria on gender equality, discrimination and sexual harassment (UB GEP)
- Non-admission of gender differences in the payment of remuneration, additional material incentives and scholarships (URAK GEP)
- Establish the appropriate measures so that there is equality between women and men in leadership and decision-making (participation, representation, training and recognition) in conditions of equity, preventing, identifying and eliminating, if any, existing gender gaps (GOBCAN GEP)

Table 2.

Gender balance in leadership and decision-making: outputs and indicators from Athena GEPs¹⁴:

Outputs	Indicators of outputs	Gender Equality Plan (institution)
Gender equality training for employees of SAV within the ATHENA project	Number of trainings performed; Number of employees trained	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Analysis of barriers to considering women's candidacy for the SAS Presidency, in the SAS House Committee and in the leadership of organisations in the 1st and 3rd Divisions of the SAS Sciences	A survey of barriers to considering women's candidacy	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Exploration of the possibilities of introducing a mentoring programme with an emphasis on young female scientists, pilot training of mentors/mentee	Design of knowledge capital, ex-current training adapted for mentoring purposes, networking (intra- and extra-institutional)	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Integration of the gender equality module into the existing training platform	Number of trainings with gender equality module available on the training platform	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Information about number of women and men in decision making bodies of UJK publicly available	Report presenting percentage number of men and women in decision making bodies of UJK published	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Monitoring the number of women and men among Directors	Available data on the number of women and men among Directors since the establishment of the Institute	Jožef Stefan Institute
Monitoring proportion (%) of women among Vice-Directors (board of vice-directors) in the previous term and current	Available data on the proportion of women and men among Advisors to the Director of the Institute	Jožef Stefan Institute

¹⁴ Gender Equality Plans of Athena Partners 2022

Monitoring the number of women and men on the Scientific Council	Available data on the proportion of women and men on the Scientific Council	Jožef Stefan Institute
Monitoring the number of women and men in the positions of heads of departments and centres	Available data on the percentage of women and men in the positions of heads of departments and centres	Jožef Stefan Institute
Monitoring the number of women and men in the key Committees within and outside of JSI	Available data on the proportion of women and men in the key committees within and outside of JSI	Jožef Stefan Institute
Team building activities between managers and employees - activities designed to engage and motivate teams to deconstruct gender stereotypes regarding leadership positions.	Available data on the influence of events on the attitude of participants. The results of the first edition will serve as indicators for future editions.	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia
Leadership training and coaching programs for women and men - Activities designed to engage and motivate teams to deconstruct gender stereotypes regarding leadership positions.	Available data on the influence of events on the attitude of participants. The results of the first edition will serve as indicators for future editions.	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia
Amending/revising some strategic UB documents, such as the University Charter, the Code of Ethics and other documents to include the principle of gender equality.	A minimum of 2 documents revised in this cycle	University of Bucharest
Increase the visibility of the commitment to gender equality in the wider community in which the University operates. By adopting the principles of the Diversity Charter in Romania.	Romanian Diversity Charter adopted and respected	University of Bucharest
Formalization of a coordination and supervision body for the promotion of	Formalised body to coordinate and oversee the promotion of gender equality at UB	University of Bucharest

gender equality at UB through a Committee for the Promotion of Gender Equality (GEPI).		
Development of the GEPI Committee: (i) adoption of specific working procedures; (ii) enlargement with representatives of other groups and associative structures	Report on the work of the GEPI Committee	University of Bucharest
Training of GEPI committee members through specific training sessions	Number of trainings	University of Bucharest
Identification and implementation of a selection procedure for an administrative team that will coordinate and monitor the GEP implementation process.	Identified and implemented procedures	University of Bucharest
Organization of a gender equality office with at least one specialized employee on gender equality within the already existing administrative structure of UB.	Functioning gender equality office	University of Bucharest
Improving the process of collecting, processing and monitoring statistical data at the institutional level to monitor and communicate gender equality indicators.	Statistical data available to monitor gender equality	University of Bucharest
Increasing the visibility of women's contribution to higher education and research through renaming of lecture theatres, classrooms, conference series, events, awards, etc.	A document with recommendations to better emphasise gender equality. Number of initiatives highlighting gender equality i.e. information on departmental websites, events dedicated to women's work, renaming of certain halls, portraits of female scientists, etc.).	University of Bucharest

Development of a communication plan and calendar of activities to promote gender equality: diversity month, women's rights month, campaign to prevent and combat domestic violence, excellence in research among women/women in science	Communications plan regarding gender equality in UB.	University of Bucharest
Introduce inclusive language in all official communications of the University of Bucharest	A guide to promoting inclusive language with explanations of terminology and specific examples	University of Bucharest
Review and Amendment Proposals and complement of the Internal acts of University related to labor remuneration, the additional material incentive and the scholarships	Number of analyzed internal documents	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Approval of the Collective Labor Agreement as an instrument for equal payment for women and men. Ensuring equality between women and men in receiving remuneration and other payments	Number of analyzed internal documents	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Keeping the awareness of the academic staff and administrative staff regarding the level of payment for women and men for the University's activities. Publicity of the regulatory framework	Number of participants.	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Try to attend to the principle of balanced presence of women and men in the appointments and designations of the positions of the management team of the management center	Number of men and women representing the ACIISI at the public contracting tables. Number of ACIISI representatives at public procurement tables with training and/or experience in gender equality	Gobierno de Canarias

Joint contracting tables promotion of gender balance among the representatives	Equal number of men and women on the scorecard. Number of people appointed with training and experience in gender.	Gobierno de Canarias
Analysis of the possible conscious or unconscious barriers that exist in the selection, promotion or hiring to ensure the representation of women in leadership and decision-making positions: structural, institutional and individual.	Number of training days and number of attendees. Number of projects approved for the third sector to promote women researchers	Gobierno de Canarias
Stimulate and give recognition to the presence of women in research and innovation teams and promote the development of content in research and technology created by women	Number of R&D&I projects granted to women and company projects led by women with respect to the total.	Gobierno de Canarias
Continue granting grants for the training of women researchers in research centers in the Canary Islands, such as the Women for Africa Foundation	Number of women beneficiaries of financing	Gobierno de Canarias

Outcomes/impact: Decision making bodies within the HEI or RPO are composed of the individuals based on their merits, experience and leadership skills and everyone willing and able to fulfill managerial position in the organization has the opportunity to apply and be evaluated in a transparent way.

Specific outcomes from GEPs¹⁵:

- Increased awareness on the issue of gender equality in management (SAS GEP)
- Increase in the ratio of women in the SAS Presidency, in the SAS House Committee and in the leadership of organisations in the 1st and 3rd Divisions of the SAS Sciences (SAS GEP)

¹⁵ Gender Equality Plans of Athena Partners 2022

- Equal leadership posts filling by representatives of both sexes (UJK GEP)
- Gender balance in the leadership positions and within the committees (JSI GEP)
- Non-admission of differences based on gender upon receipt of remuneration from the University and the provision of scholarships (URAK GEP)
- Ensuring equality between women and men in receiving remuneration and other payments (URAK GEP)
- Ensuring the equal opportunities of women and men to be involved in decision-making jobs in the University (URAK GEP)
- Parity in ACIISI representation in procurement tables. All ACIISI representatives on the procurement tables have training and/or experience in gender equality (GOBCAN GEP)
- Parity is maintained on the scorecard (GOBCAN GEP)
- Increase the number of designated individuals with gender education and experience (GOBCAN GEP)
- Maintain the funding allocated to the third sector to promote female scientists and maintain the number of female beneficiaries of this funding (GOBCAN GEP)

Indicators of outcomes¹⁶:

1. Women among Directors of the institution
2. Proportion of women among Vice-Directors
3. Proportion of women on scientific boards
4. Proportion of women among Deans of Faculties in the given year
5. Proportion of women among Vice-Deans of Faculties
6. Glass Ceiling Index
7. Gender-integrated leadership programme
8. Gender training for managers
9. Targets/quotas for gender balance in boards and committees

¹⁶ Gender Equality Audit Indicators Handbook, Athena Project Deliverable 2021, Gender Equality Index 2019. Work-life balance

Specific Indicators of outcomes from GEPs¹⁷

- Level of awareness regarding gender equality in the management (SAS GEP)
- The ratio of women in the SAS Presidency, in the SAS House Committee and in the leadership of organisations in the 1st and 3rd Divisions of the SAS Sciences (SAS GEP)
- Percentage number of men and women in decision making bodies of UJK presented in a publicly available report (UJK GEP)
- Gender of the Director of the Institute (JSI GEP)
- Proportion (%) of women among Vice-Directors (board of vice-directors) in the previous term and current term (JSI GEP) (JSI GEP)
- Proportion (%) of women among heads of departments and centres (JSI GEP)
- Proportion (%) of women in the Election Committee (JSI GEP)
- Number of women and men in the key Committees within the Institute (e.g. Expert Council, Expert Councils for Research and Infrastructure, Investment Commission, Nuclear and Radiation Commission, Reactor Safety Committee) (JSI GEP)
- Number of women and men nominated (by JSI) to the Commissions or Committees of Institutions operating in the field of science (Slovenian Research Agency (SRA), Ministry for Education, Science and Sports, SPIRIT and elsewhere where JSI is invited to nominate candidates (JSI GEP)
- Number of women and men among employees who understand and implement the need for deconstruction (FRCT GEP)
- At least 3 days are held with 75% of the staff attending (GOBCAN GEP)
- The number of R&D&i projects granted to women and company projects led by women is maintained or increased with respect to the total (GOBCAN GEP)

¹⁷ Gender Equality Plans of Athena Partners 2022

3.3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

Description of the area of intervention: Gender bias is widespread at work and in organisations, creating inequalities at every stage of the employment cycle. Gender-based stereotypes affect how candidates get recruited for certain roles, whether candidates get selected for those roles and why, how salaries are negotiated, how managers provide feedback to their employees, and how development opportunities are divided between employees. Each of these factors compounds across women's careers, producing and sustaining gender inequality from recruitment through selection to promotion. The same situation women face along their career path in innovation and research. Women are often underrepresented in the higher paid jobs and their careers develop slower than those of men. The Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 states that women and men in all their diversity should have equal opportunities to thrive and be economically independent, be paid equally for their work of equal value, have equal access to finance and receive fair pensions¹⁸. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression is not isolated from other areas of intervention mainly: gender balance in leadership and decision-making and work-life balance¹⁹. Potential measures that could be taken under this intervention: establishing codes of conduct for recruitment and promotion, involving gender equality expertise in recruitment and promotion committees, providing unconscious bias training for recruiters, reviewing language used in adverts and increasing awareness of language biases in recommendation letter.

Objectives:

1. Develop and implement procedures to counteract gender-based stereotypes at every stage of the employment cycle
2. Provide necessary conditions for monitoring and evaluation of gender equality in recruitment and career progression.

Specific objectives from GEPs:

- Promoting gender equality in the recruitment process (SAS GEP)
- Sensitising employees to gender equality issues in recruitment and career development (SAS GEP)
- Strengthening gender equality in senior research degrees and among postdoctoral fellows (SAS GEP)
- Measuring income inequalities by gender (SAS GEP)

¹⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0152>

¹⁹ Horizon Europe Guidelines on Gender Equality Plans 2021

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ffcb06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1>

- Facilitated return to work after maternity or paternity leave (UJK GEP)
- Achieving gender balance in employment decisions committees (UJK GEP)
- Increasing the participation of women in the recruitment process (UJK GEP)
- Developing a sense of security in career development (UJK GEP)
- Ensuring that women and men have equal opportunities to develop and advance professionally (JSI GEP)
- Preventing any discrimination based on gender in the HR processes (JSI GEP)
- Providing equal access to career development to young researchers regardless of their gender (JSI GEP)
- Ensuring that access to funding is not gender biased (JSI GEP)
- Guaranteeing that awarding process is not gender biased (JSI GEP)
- Guaranteeing the principle of equality and non-discrimination between women and men in recruitment and career progression (FRCT GEP)
- Promoting equal career opportunities (ULPGC GEP)
- Increasing awareness and knowledge of the reasons hindering women's career advancement (ULPGC GEP)
- Increasing gender equality in recruitment and career advancement (UB GEP)
- Observing and promoting the equality of women and men in decision-making processes in the management bodies of RUAK, as well as in the management bodies of the main units and service units (URAK GEP)
- Implement the necessary measures to prevent and act, if any, against discrimination based on sex in hiring and professional promotion, guaranteeing gender equality (GOBCAN GEP)

Table 3.

Gender equality in recruitment and career progression: outputs and indicators from Athena GEPs²⁰

Outputs	Indicators of outputs	Gender Equality Plan (institution)
Promoting gender equality in the recruitment process (in synergy with activity HRS4R), including recommendations to avoid conflicts of interest in the selection process from a gender equality perspective	Document containing the recommendations to avoid conflicts of interest in the selection process from a gender equality perspective	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Ensure the use of gender-sensitive language in advertisements and welcome packs in line with HRS4R activities	Report	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Gender equality training for the employees of SAV within the ATHENA project	Number of employees trained	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Barrier survey, Communication between P SAS and SAS organisations on the preparation of conditions for the progression to higher degrees	Document containing the analysis of barriers	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Preparation of calculation and data acquisition methodology	Document containing data	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Assess needs and develop solutions to facilitate return to work after maternity or paternity leave	Report containing information on the needs arising after returning to work From maternity or paternity leave	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Transparency in the recruitment process	Number of modified/designed transparency procedures	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce

²⁰ Gender Equality Plans of Athena Partners 2022

A high standard of transparency in job advertisements	Number of job advertisements/job competitions/promotion opportunities created in inclusive language	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Promoting gender equality in the recruitment process	Number of modified/designed transparency procedures	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Maintaining the transparency of the regulations and criteria for admission to university and doctoral schools	Number of modified/designed transparency procedures	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Monitoring the proportion of women and men among all employees and their salaries	Available data on proportion (%) of women among total number of employees in the organisation (all types of contract) and the differences in salaries between women and men on the similar positions	Jožef Stefan Institute
Monitoring the proportion of women and men among researchers, taking into account A grade researchers and how this proportion changes within time	Available data on the number of women and men among researchers in different age cohorts	Jožef Stefan Institute
Understanding the gender distribution among different research areas	Available data on the number of women and men researchers depending on the research area	Jožef Stefan Institute
Providing equal access to postdoctoral training and abroad development opportunities to women and men researchers	Available data on the number of women and men researchers who went abroad for postdoctoral training	Jožef Stefan Institute
Providing equal access to funding	Analysis of funds distribution from the gender perspective	Jožef Stefan Institute
Ensure that both women and men have access to scientific awards	Analysis of nomination and awarded researchers from the gender perspective	Jožef Stefan Institute
Promoting Gender neutral recruitment and hiring to implement job-shadowing program. (Original Idea: Sabanci University - HEI - Turkey)	Report containing information how to implement of a mentoring programme to enable women to achieve leadership competencies and facilitate their promotion.	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia

Recognising domestic and family care skills in the Curriculum Vitae of candidates	Documents containing a holistic evaluation of candidates' curriculum vitae	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia
Understanding the gender distribution among departments and projects of employees, collaborators and grantees with particular reference to IT department.	Available data on the number of women and men departments and projects of employees, collaborators and grantees with particular reference to IT department	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia
Ensure that under-represented gender groups are given preference in the five main branches of knowledge to guarantee the promotion of GEP.	Document containing information on the verification of the inclusion of the affirmative action measure	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Include in the scale, an additional score in order to give preference to women in STEM (science and engineering) positions.	Report containing information on the verification of the additional scale score	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Guarantee the balanced representation of women and men in the access commissions for the selection of teaching and research staff and administrative staff.	Annual report containing compliance check	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Ensure that women have equal access to promotion	Annual analysis of any difficulties women may have in promotion.	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Take appropriate measures to mitigate the identified difficulties that women have on the promotion path.	Report containing the results of the survey and, where appropriate, verifying the action taken.	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Training and sensitizing Human Resources staff on	Training and awareness-raising program which will incorporate	Universitatea din Bucuresti

the principle of gender equality on the labor market and in the university environment.	elements such as creating equal opportunities for employment and promotion, provisions related to parental leave and other forms of leave and benefits for caring for family members, provisions related to sexual and moral harassment at work.	
Increasing the level of knowledge and understanding of the ethical obligations associated with an academic career, including the obligations to prevent gender discrimination, and prevent and discourage sexual harassment.	Pilot program to raise awareness on the requirements of an academic career through a short online training on professional ethical obligations, including non-discrimination, prevention and deterrence of sexual harassment, and the principle of equal opportunities between women and men.	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Revising the framework methodology for awarding professional degrees to teaching and administrative staff.	Report containing an analysis of data on the evolution of women-men ratio in the number of gradations awarded and the development of a gender sensitive framework methodology for awarding professional gradations to teaching and administrative staff.	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Monitoring the professional trajectory of UB graduates with the presentation of gender-disaggregated data	Annual reports on the professional trajectory of UB graduates.	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Guaranteeing equal opportunities for the participation of women and men in decision-making processes in the structures of the University	Number of women and men involved in decision-making	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Establish and publicly announce transparent selection criteria for	Number of documents on the internal webpage of URAK about the election procedures	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev

governing bodies, in line with the principle of equality between women and men		
Include in the call application forms a specific field to collect whether the company or institution has an equality plan and a declaration of responsibility in the case of companies with more than 50 workers required by law.	Number of companies and institutions that have a voluntary/mandatory equality plan compared to the total number of those that have been presented. Number of companies that deliver the responsible statement compared to the total.	Gobierno de Canarias
Include in the external audits aimed at the institutions that receive funds that they have to comply with the current legislation on equality and accredit it: depending on whether more than 50 workers is a voluntary or mandatory equality plan and remuneration record disaggregated by sex	Number of audits that include information on the obligation to comply with equality legislation: remuneration record + equality plan Number of companies that accredit it + 50 workers -50 workers on a voluntary basis.	Gobierno de Canarias
Continue collecting and analyzing disaggregated data on men and women hired by financed institutions and companies to identify possible gender gaps.	Number of women and men beneficiaries of the financing	Gobierno de Canarias
Continue to include in the regulatory bases of subsidies and all calls for funding with public funds for R&D&I, criteria that favor the hiring of women through positive discrimination measures.	Number of R&D&I projects granted to women and company projects led by women with respect to the total	Gobierno de Canarias

Outcomes/impact: All students and academic/research staff regardless of their gender and family status have the ability to develop their careers within the HEI or RPO.

Specific outcomes from GEPs²¹

- More women participate in recruitment processes (UJK GEP)
- More women develop their careers (UJK GEP)
- There is a gender balance in employment decisions committees (UJK GEP)
- There are procedures to facilitate return to work after maternity and parental leave. (UJK GEP)
- More women with senior research degrees and among postdoctoral fellows (SAS GEP)
- Reducing income inequality (SAS GEP)
- Employees on the same positions with the same responsibilities earn the same level of salaries (SAS GEP)
- Increasing number of researchers of the underrepresented sex in the research areas where gender inequality among research staff is evident (JSI GEP)
- Women and men have the same access to funding opportunities for research
- Women and men are evaluated on the same terms while being nominated to and awarded with scientific prizes (JSI GEP)
- More women has participate in the mentoring program. (FRCT GEP)
- More recruiters take the skills acquired in housework and caring into account as valuable when recruiting (FRCT GEP)
- More women recruited in areas where gender disparity was detected (FRCT GEP)
- Keeping the equal opportunities for the participation of women and men in decision-making processes in the structures of the University (URAK GEP)

²¹ Gender Equality Plans of all Athena Partners 2022

- Publicity of the information on the internal page of the University and in the archive with the decisions of the Academic Council (URAK GEP)

Indicators of outcomes²²:

1. Proportion of women among PhD applicants
2. Proportion of women among all and new doctoral students
3. Proportion of women among doctoral graduates in 2016 and 2020
4. Distribution of ISCED 8 graduates across broad fields of study, by sex
5. Proportion of persons with precarious working contracts among researchers
6. Annual number of researchers on care leave by sex
7. Pay transparency policies
8. Gender pay audits/equality pay reports prepared and publicly available
9. Appropriated workload and content of the work policy
10. Non-discriminatory equipment necessary for work/research measures

Specific Indicators of outcomes from GEPs²³:

1. Number of job advertisements/job competitions/promotion opportunities created in inclusive language; design of job (UJK GEP)
2. Gender balance in recruitment committees (UJK GEP)
3. Number of academic staff, students and PhD candidates registering for gender equality training (SAS GEP)
4. Number of women among senior researchers and post-doctoral fellows (SAS GEP)
5. Average gross monthly earnings of researchers paid in the given year, by gender and habilitation level (JSI GEP)
6. Proportion (%) of persons employed part-time among researchers by gender (JSI GEP)
7. Number of years between first and full-time employment by gender (JSI GEP)
8. Distribution (%) of researchers employed across age groups, by gender (Age cohorts: 25–34; 35–44; 45–54; 55- 64; 65 and over) (JSI GEP)
9. Distribution (%) of researchers in the fields of Electronics and Information Technology; Chemistry, Biology, Materials and

²² Gender Equality Audit Indicators Handbook, Athena Project Deliverable 2021

²³ Gender Equality Plans of all Athena Partners 2022

- Environmental Sciences; Physics and Reactor Engineering, by gender (JSI GEP)
10. Proportion (%) of women among academic staff, by academic grade (JSI GEP)
 11. Proportion (%) of A grade women (professors) among all A grade staff by the main fields of Research and Development (JSI GEP)
 12. Number of applicants for Young Researchers grants, by gender (JSI GEP)
 13. Proportion (%) of women among PhD graduates in calendar year (JSI GEP)
 14. Proportion (%) of women among new doctors in a calendar year in the in the different research fields (JSI GEP)
 15. Number of doctors who went abroad for postdoctoral training in a calendar year, by gender (JSI GEP)
 16. Number of doctors who returned from postdoctoral training abroad in a calendar year and (re) employed at JSI, by gender (JSI GEP)
 17. Number of applicants - principal investigators of research funding for a given year in national funds, by sex (JSI GEP)
 18. Success rate (by gender) in funding national research projects for JSI researchers as principal investigators in the past year. Difference in success rate in obtaining funding of national research project between men and women as principal investigators from JSI applying for national research funds for the given year (JSI GEP)
 19. Number of women and men selected to fund the Early Career Researchers program (JSI GEP)
 20. Number of researchers leading an industrial project, by gender (JSI GEP)
 21. Number of researchers leading a national research (SRA) program, by gender (JSI GEP)
 22. The average grants' amounts allocated to research projects conducted by men and women - principal investigators from national research funds at the level of organisation for the given year (JSI GEP)
 23. The average grants' amounts allocated to research projects conducted by men and women - principal investigators (international research funds) (at the level of organisation) for the given year (EUR) (JSI GEP)
 24. Number of women and men from the Institute nominated for specific Award (JSI GEP)

25. Number of women and men from the Institute among the winners of the specific Award (JSI GEP)
26. Numbers of analysis sheets including information on how to assess skills acquired in housework and caring (FRCT GEP)
27. Number of women in leadership positions (FRCT GEP)
28. Number of women recruited in areas where gender disparity was detected (FRCT GEP)
29. The number of R&D&I projects whose content includes the gender dimension is maintained or increased (GOBCAN GEP)
30. The number of awarded companies that have a voluntary/mandatory equality plan compared to the total number of those that have been presented increases.
Number of awarded companies that deliver the responsible statement compared to the total increases (GOBCAN GEP)
31. Number of awarded companies that deliver the responsible statement compared to the total (GOBCAN GEP)

3.4. Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content

Description of the area of intervention: The reason why actions advancing gender equality in the HEI and RPO are particularly important is that research and educational outputs have tremendous impact on the society and economy. In order to make sure that research and innovation as well as teaching content is not gender biased certain methodologies ensuring gender mainstreaming at all levels of research and academic work are required. Funding schemes should ensure gender expertise in the evaluation process and research teams/academic staff should be aware of how to include gender dimension in their work.²⁴ The Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 states that without inclusive leadership the EU will not be able to bring forward new ideas and innovative approaches that will contribute to society. Therefore integrating gender dimension into research and teaching content is essential for the sustainable and innovative EU.²⁵

Objectives²⁶:

1. Ensure that sex and gender analysis is considered in the design and outputs of research and teaching.
2. Understand the impact of research projects on women and men regardless of the scientific area.
3. Support researchers in developing methodologies that incorporate the gender dimension.
4. Ensure that sex and gender analysis is considered in the design and outputs of research and teaching.
5. Understand the impact of research projects on women and men regardless of the scientific area.
6. Support researchers in developing methodologies that incorporate the gender dimension.

²⁴ Horizon Europe Guidelines on Gender Equality Plans 2021

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ffcb06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1>

²⁵ A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2020%3A152%3AFIN>

²⁶ Ibidem

Specific objectives from GEPs ²⁷:

- Promoting gender issues in research and teaching (SAS GEP)
- Implementation of an analytical focus on gender equality in research project applications (VEGA and international projects) (SAS GEP)
- Regular monitoring of gender in SAS research (SAS GEP)
- Creation of an expert platform of male and female staff who integrate a gender perspective into their research (SAS GEP)
- Promoting gender equality among members of UJK community (UJK GEP)
- Providing trainings on the topics related to gender equality among members of the UJK community (UJK GEP)
- Disseminating knowledge about women scientists (UJK GEP)
- Promoting gender dimension in research by organizing workshops and trainings and discussion (JSI GEP)
- Promoting the use and gender sensitive language (JSI GEP)
- Ensuring women's participation and representation in project development and access to research funding (FRCT GEP)
- Familiarization of UB teachers and researchers with the strategy of gender mainstreaming (GM) in academic research (UB GEP)
- Financial allocation at UB level for research projects that propose a gender mainstreaming approach (UB GEP)
- Starting a research program on the contribution of women to the development of higher education and research in Romania (UB GEP)
- Development of a platform on the ICUB website dedicated to research in the field of gender equality (UB GEP)
- Starting an interdisciplinary research plan with a gender component (UB GEP)
- Overcoming gender stereotypes in various spheres of public life and sexism (URAK GEP)

²⁷ Gender Equality Plans of all Athena Partners 2022

- Include the gender perspective in research actions, educational and communicative content, identifying and eliminating all sexist biases and stereotypes, if any (GOBCAN GEP)
- Carry out the programming, collection and monitoring of data disaggregated by sex, including specific indicators for measuring budget allocation and gender impact (how much it benefits men or women and the reduction of existing gaps) of strategies, plans, programs, calls and projects that are financed by public funds (GOBCAN GEP)

Table 4.

Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content: outputs and indicators from from Athena GEPs²⁸:

Outputs	Indicators of outputs	Gender Equality Plan (institution)
Gender equality training for employees of SAV within the ATHENA project	Number of trainings performed; Number of employees trained	Slovak Academy of Sciences
An event on implementation of an analytical focus on gender equality in research project applications (VEGA and international projects)	Number of event participants	Slovak Academy of Sciences
An item on gender mainstreaming in research and teaching added to the structure of the annual report	Amendment to the structure of the annual report	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Exploration of staffing options to create an expert platform that will subsequently sponsor some of the GEP activities from other objectives	The basis for the platform established	Slovak Academy of Sciences

²⁸ Gender Equality Plans of Athena Partners 2022

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

Creation and update of the website or e-learning platform dedicated to gender equality	Increase in the number of page entries	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Regular trainings for academic staff, students and PhD candidates, incl the topic of unconscious bias	Number of trainings performed; Number of employees and students/PhD candidates trained	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Design of e-learning materials regarding gender equality	Number of materials designed	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Series of events presenting academic and research career pathway from the gender perspective	Number of events organized per year; Number of events' participants	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Establishment of scientific club focused on equality	Number of Scientific Club Members; Report from the Scientific club activity	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Inclusion of the equal treatment thematic into the curricula of BA/MA studies and PhD School	Number of curricula (BA/MA studies and PhD Schools) which include equal treatment	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Support for research and academic staff as well as PhD candidates in performing research projects with focus on gender equality	Number of projects/publications/dissertations including gender equality as a research topic	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Increase the awareness in gender dimension and research	Number of trainings for using gender in research and teaching	Jožef Stefan Institute
Increase the awareness that gender dimension is a part of scientific projects	Number of projects involving the gender dimension in the calendar year	Jožef Stefan Institute
Increase opportunities for women in science to receive sponsorship, grants, awards for women scientists.	Number of women participants in "Women in Science Award"	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia
Recognising and promoting women in science	Number of events, workshops aimed at integrating the gender dimension into research and science	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia

Organizing a pilot training program on gender mainstreaming.	Pilot training programme on gender mainstreaming	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Develop an informal interdisciplinary and interdepartmental network of researchers who take a gender mainstreaming approach.	Established an informal interdisciplinary and interdepartmental network	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Developing a priority funding area for research projects that have a gender mainstreaming approach.	A dedicated priority funding area for research projects that have a gender-sensitive approach.	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Development of a platform on the ICUB website for research in the field.	A functioning platform on the ICUB website for research in this area.	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Creating a register with researchers from the University of Bucharest specialized/with interests in this field	Register with researchers from the University of Bucharest specialised/interested in the field of gender equality	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Launching a gender studies course at the university	Number of students in each year	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Launching an interdisciplinary summer school in gender studies for undergraduate students	Number of summer school participants	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Launch of a pilot study on the gender dimension in the curriculum in one of the faculties	Research report containing the results of a pilot study on the gender dimension of the curriculum in one of the faculties	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Develop an interdisciplinary research plan on gender equality issues, focusing on relevant issues relating to the 8 thematic areas of the GEP	Document containing an interdisciplinary research agenda on gender equality issues	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Establishing an informal network of researchers interested in interdisciplinary research in the field	Partnerships established	Universitatea din Bucuresti

Promotion of measures for effective implementation of the policy on equality between women and men.	Publicity of the procedure and its results	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Implementation of an information policy in the University system to raise the awareness of students, academic staff and administrative staff regarding the principle of equality between women and men.	Number of published documents on the internal website of the University	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Providing a link to the rubric "Equal opportunities" maintained by the Ministry of Labor and Social Policy.	Existence of this link on the university website	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Organization of meetings - talks between students, academic staff and the representatives of the central and local authorities (coordinators for equality between women and men)	Number of participants	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Organizing the presentation of information on the benefits to society and the economy of equality between women and men by representatives of the central or local government	Number of participants	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Holding talks with representatives of the central and local authorities to raise awareness of the new challenges that have an impact on the equality of women and men - new technologies, digital industries, artificial intelligence, transition to a green and digital economy, the need for new skills and new jobs, climate change, migration, threats to public health such as pandemics,	Number of participants	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev

possible conflicts disrupting peace and security, etc.		
Guarantee the dimension of gender equality in the contents of all R&D projects that are supported	Number of R&D&i projects granted whose content contemplates the gender dimension	Gobierno de Canarias
Guarantee gender equality in the award of public contracts	Number of awarded companies that have a voluntary/mandatory equality plan compared to the total number of those that have been presented. Number of awarded companies that deliver the responsible statement compared to the total.	Gobierno de Canarias
Verify through the reports that the projects supported with funding have been implemented from a gender perspective, identifying possible gender gaps and establishing the appropriate mechanisms to eliminate them, if any	Number of funded projects implemented from a gender perspective	Gobierno de Canarias
Maintain in applications for grants and aid a field of the applicant disaggregated by sex and prepare reports on the budgets granted to men and women	Annual budget granted to men and women	Gobierno de Canarias
Review specific data disaggregated by sex from the last calls granted to see if there are gender gaps	Number of men and women beneficiaries of each action during the period 2020 – 2025	Gobierno de Canarias
Create a dashboard with indicators disaggregated by sex with all the data collected in the application for all subsidies, carry out analyzes and proposals for possible corrective measures, if applicable	Number of working groups in which ACIISI participates	Gobierno de Canarias
Continue participating in the gender equality working groups on behalf of the ACIISI R&D&i funds and	Number of working groups in which ACIISI participate	Gobierno de Canarias

policies		
Include specific objectives in programs related to the promotion of gender equality	Number of programs promoting gender equality	Gobierno de Canarias

Outcomes/impact: Research and teaching content is free from gender-bias .

Specific outcomes from GEPs²⁹:

- Increased awareness on how to include gender issues in research and teaching (SAS GEP)
- Integration of gender analysis into research (SAS GEP)
- Raised accessibility of information about gender equality among members of the UJK community (UJK GEP)
- Raised awareness about gender equality among members of the UJK community (UJK GEP)
- Increased interest in scientific work among women (UJK GEP)
- Increased interest in gender equality as a research topic (UJK GEP)
- Staff are aware of the gender dimension and its importance and know gender-sensitive language (JSI GEP)
- Promoting women in science to receive more grants, awards for their projects (FRCT GEP)
- Increased interest in integrating the gender dimension in science (FRCT GEP)
- Increased awareness on how to include gender issues in research and teaching (UB GEP)
- Integration of gender analysis into research and curricula (UB GEP)
- Limitation of the opportunities to have discriminative actions (URAK GEP)
- Promotion of the national policy on equality between women and men in national and international events (URAK GEP)
- Raising the awareness of University staff about the social importance of equality between women and men (URAK GEP)

²⁹ Gender Equality Plans of Athena Partners 2022

- Raising the awareness of the academic, administrative and student staff of the University about the social significance of equality between women and men (URAK GEP)
- Keep track of budget items disaggregated by sex (GOBCAN GEP)
- Increase the number of ACIISI personnel that participate in these working groups (GOBCAN GEP)
- Maintain/increase the number of programs of this type (GOBCAN GEP)

Indicators of outcomes³⁰:

1. Funding success rate difference between women and men applying for the national funds
2. Funding success rate difference between women and men applying for the international funds
3. The average grants' amounts allocated to research projects from national funds
4. The average grants' amounts allocated to research projects from international funds
5. Funding success rate difference between women and men national coordinators applying for the international funds
6. Proportion of research projects including gender dimension within the research objectives among all research projects performed
7. Gender budgeting
8. Women networks established
9. External alliances of organisations with an outstanding reputation for gender equality created
10. GE awareness-raising activities for students
11. GE awareness-raising activities for staff

Specific Indicators of outcomes from GEPs³¹

- Number of research projects including an analytical focus on gender equality (SAS GEP)
- Number of academic staff, students and PhD candidates using online tools providing information on gender equality (UJK GEP)

³⁰ Gender Equality Audit Indicators Handbook, Athena Project Deliverable 2021, Gender Equality Index 2019. Work-life balance

³¹ Gender Equality Plans of Athena Partners 2022

- Number of academic staff, students and PhD candidates registering for gender equality trainings (UJK GEP)
- Proportion of women among post-docs (UJK GEP)
- Proportion of gender equality oriented research projects (UJK GEP)
- Number of women receiving grants, awards (JSI GEP)
- Numbers of trainings for using gender in research and teaching (JSI GEP)
- Number of projects involving the gender dimension in the calendar year (JSI GEP)
- Number of projects integrating the gender dimension (FRCT GEP).
- The number of R&D&I projects whose content includes the gender dimension is maintained or increased (GOBCAN GEP)
- The number of awarded companies that have a voluntary/mandatory equality plan compared to the total number of those that have been presented increases. Number of awarded companies that deliver the responsible statement compared to the total increases (GOBCAN GEP)
- Number of awarded companies that deliver the responsible statement compared to the total (GOBCAN GEP)
- Identify gender gaps (GOBCAN GEP)
- Have a control panel that allows the visualization and analysis of the information from the historical data (GOBCAN GEP)

3.5. Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment

Gender-based violence including sexual harassment is a phenomenon deeply rooted in gender inequality, and continues to be one of the most notable human rights violations within all societies. Gender-based violence is violence directed against a person because of their gender. Both women and men experience gender-based violence but the majority of victims are women and girls³². Sexual harassment is often underestimated in research organisations and universities. Therefore HEI and RPO should take measures to combat gender based violence and sexual harassment. They should address following dimensions³³ : behaviours, reporting, support for victims, investigation, disciplinary measures and prosecutions.

Objectives:

1. Establish and codify the expected behaviours of employees and students to prevent gender-based violence
2. Provide institutional framework and procedures to support victims and draw consequences for perpetrators
3. Provide institutional framework and procedures for protection against gender-based violence and for the prevention of complaints of gender-based violence
4. Raise awareness of gender-based violence among students, academics/researchers and administrative staff

Specific objectives from GEPs³⁴:

- Sensitising staff to gender equality issues in the area of gender-based violence, including sexual harassment (SAS GEP)
- Establishment of a guideline to prevent and address gender-based violence and sexual harassment (SAS GEP)
- Reduction in the incidence of gender-based violence (UJK GEP)

³² <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-based-violence/what-is-gender-based-violence>

³³ Horizon Europe Guidelines on Gender Equality Plans 2021

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ffcb06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1>

³⁴ Gender Equality Plans of Athena Partners 2022

- Building a community free from gender-based violence (UJK GEP)
- Increasing awareness of the various forms and incidence of gender-based violence in the working environment (JSI GEP)
- Establishment and promotion of clear procedures for employees to report incidents of gender-based violence and sexual harassment (JSI GEP)
- Establishment a procedure to collect information on gender-based violence and sexual harassment in order to prevent it (JSI GEP)
- Preventing and combating harassment at work and other forms of harm to the physical or moral integrity, freedom and dignity of male and female employees (FRCT GEP)
- Using inclusive language, either in a gender-neutral way or by referring to both genders and acquire tools to apply inclusive language (FRCT GEP)
- Raise awareness to prevent sexual and gender-based harassment (ULPGC GEP)
- Establishing an effective and transparent mechanism for investigating incidents of sexual harassment and gender discrimination in UB (UB GEP)
- Combating violence and protecting and supporting victims (URAK GEP)
- Ensure the necessary measures to prevent, identify and act against sexist violence, if any, including sexual and gender-based harassment in the institutional sphere of the ACIISI ((GOBCAN GEP)
- Guarantee that all external and internal communication is carried out with inclusive language and free of content and/or images that include sexist stereotypes (GOBCAN GEP)

Table 5.

Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment: outputs and indicators from Athena GEPs³⁵

Outputs	Indicators of outputs	Gender Equality Plan (institution)
Gender-based violence training for directors of SAS organisations and trade union representatives (possibly for other target groups)	Number of employees trained	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Gender equality training for SAS staff in the framework of the ATHENA project (including training of trainers)	Number of employees trained	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Design and implementation an internal regulation against gender-based violence and sexual harassment (in synergy with HRS4R)	Document containing the internal regulation against gender-based violence and sexual harassment (in synergy with HRS4R)	Slovak Academy of Sciences
Study on awareness of gender-based violence and sexual harassment	Document containing information on awareness of gender-based violence and sexual harassment among students and academic staff	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce
Creation of a methodology for monitoring sexual harassment incidents	Document containing a description of methodology	Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce

³⁵ ibidem

Establish a contact person for handling gender-based violence, mobbing, sexual harassment	Monitoring the number of people involved in violence and sexual harassment and number of cases	Jožef Štefan Institute
Increase awareness by discussions and organized workshops	Seminars and trainings organized to cover the topic of gender based violence	Jožef Štefan Institute
Diagnose the prevalence of sexual harassment in the organisation by designed and implemented survey	Document containing results of the survey	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia
Setting up a focal point which will prevent a sexual harassment and offer support when/if needed.	Trained specialist	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia
Creating the internal lecture event with a professional qualified in the area of gender violence	Number of participants	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia
Developing guidelines for gender sensitive and inclusive language	Document containing rules how to use language in inclusive gender sensitive way.	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia
Evaluate the protocol for detection, prevention and action in cases of sexual and gender-based harassment.	Adequate protocols addressing all types of harassment	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria

<p>Promote activities to disseminate the Protocol on Sexual and Gender-Based Harassment to the university community.</p>	<p>Number and type of actions carried out biannually</p>	<p>Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria</p>
<p>Promoting awareness-raising and training activities on the prevention of gender-based violence</p>	<p>Number and type of actions undertaken</p>	<p>Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria</p>
<p>Analysis of the application of the Protocol on Sexual and Gender-Based Harassment</p>	<p>Report on the analysis of the application of the Protocol on Sexual and Gender-Based Harassment.</p>	<p>Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria</p>
<p>Development of procedures on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recording and investigating cases of sexual harassment and gender discrimination. - Counselling petitioners. -Conducting investigations and reporting on the results. -Informing about the operation of the mechanism and how to complain about sexual harassment cases. 	<p>Operating procedures</p>	<p>Universitatea din Bucuresti</p>
<p>Development of an anti-discrimination and anti-sexual harassment campaign at UB implemented by students through student associations and</p>	<p>Number of campaigns and their audiences</p>	<p>Universitatea din Bucuresti</p>

partnerships with relevant NGOs		
Developing training material (possibly online) on combating sexual harassment and gender discrimination.	Online training program on combating sexual harassment and gender discrimination.	Universitatea din Bucuresti
Prevention against violence, as violation of human rights and form of discrimination gender based	Number of normative acts prohibiting discrimination, published on the University website	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Organisation of meetings and public lectures with representatives of the Discrimination Commission or the judiciary on the prohibition of discrimination and non-violence	Number of participants	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Organization of a scientific conference at the University (Faculty of Law) on the issues of prohibition of discrimination and measures to combat violence.	Number of participants of the conference	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
Taking effective measures to prevent all forms of discrimination in the workplace and at school by persons from the teaching or non-teaching staff or by students.	Number of analysed internal documents	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev

Keep ACIISI staff informed about the protocol for action in situations of harassment in the workplace of the Public Administration of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands	Number of training sessions given to ACIISI staff during the period of validity of this Equality Plan	Gobierno de Canarias
Continue including in the bases of subsidies and in the specifications the necessary compliance with European regulations related to support for the hiring of women victims of sexist violence	Number of financial actions that contain references to compliance with regulations related to support for victims of gender violence	Gobierno de Canarias
Continue to include in external audits aimed at institutions that receive funds the obligation to comply with current legislation on equality and specifically to approve and apply a protocol for prevention and action against sexual and gender-based harassment.	Number of entities/individuals benefiting from the funding actions that apply a protocol against sexual and gender-based harassment	Gobierno de Canarias
Dissemination and implementation of gender-sensitive communication guidelines	Number of training pills disseminated aimed at gender awareness	Gobierno de Canarias
Carrying out a language review from a gender perspective: web, social networks, internal and external communications to identify areas for improvement in order to use	Percentage of reviewed publications that do not contain inclusive language	Gobierno de Canarias

inclusive visual and textual communication		
Continue naming performances in honor of women scientists.	Number of performances in tribute to scientific women	Gobierno de Canarias
Continue activities on women and girls in science through mini-fairs	Number of mini-fairs held on women and girls in science	Gobierno de Canarias
Continue including the gender dimension in relation to inclusive and non-sexist communication and advertising in the bases and criteria for assessment	Number of actions in which compliance with inclusive and non-sexist communication and advertising is verified	Gobierno de Canarias

Outcomes/impact: All students and academics/researchers, regardless of gender do not experience gender-based violence. If they do, they know what measures to take to protect themselves. All complaints are treated seriously and responded to appropriately using a trauma-informed approach.

Specific outcomes from GEPs³⁶:

- A community free of gender-based violence (UJK GEP)
- Reduction in the incidence of gender-based violence (UJK GEP)
- Staff recognise and understand gender equality issues in relation to gender-based violence, including sexual harassment (SAS GEP)

³⁶ Gender Equality Plans of Athena Partners 2022

- A guideline to prevent and address gender-based violence and sexual harassment (SAS GEP)
- Academic staff recognise and understand gender equality issues in relation to gender-based violence, including sexual harassment (JSI GEP)
- Internal document containing procedures to prevent gender-based violence (JSI GEP)
- A guideline for gender sensitive and inclusive language (FRCT GEP)
- The university community is aware of what gender-based violence is and knows how to prevent it (ULPGC GEP)
- The university community knows all the anti-violence procedures and how to use them.(UB Romania)
- Publicise information on the university's internal website and archive with Academic Board decisions (URAK GEP)
- Awareness of the academic staff and administrative staff (URAK GEP)
- Awareness of the academic staff and administrative staff (URAK GEP)
- Limitation of the opportunities to implement discriminative actions based on the data (URAK GEP)
- Achieve the widest possible dissemination of these measures (GOBCAN GEP)

Indicators of outcomes³⁷:

1. Protocol for preventing and tackling sexual harassment and gender-based violence
2. Promotion of awareness measures to prevent harassment, sexist attitudes
3. Internal guidelines/measures on the use of non-sexist language in internal and external communication
4. Specific person/committee/commission responsible for harassment at the institutional level
5. Bodies mandated to implement and monitor policy of 'non-discrimination on the basis of gender'.

³⁷ Horizon Europe Guidelines on Gender Equality Plans 2021
<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ffcb06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1>

Specific Indicators of outcomes from GEPs³⁸

- The number of cases of gender-based violence (UJK GEP)
- Number of academic staff, students and PhD candidates registering for awareness-raising training on gender-based violence (UJK GEP)
- Number of academic staff, students and PhD candidates familiar with internal regulation against gender-based violence and sexual harassment (SAS GEP)
- Number of directors of SAS organisations and representatives of trade union registering for awareness-raising training on gender-based violence (SAS GEP)
- Internal regulation against gender-based violence and sexual harassment implemented (SAS GEP)
- Monitoring number of people and cases involved in violence and sexual harassment at JSI (JSI GEP)
- Number of employees who have received appropriate support in cases of gender-based violence, mobbing or sexual harassment (JSI GEP)
- All documents of the organisation written in inclusive language (FRCT GEP).
- The number of financial actions that comply with it is maintained or increased (GOBCAN I GEP)
- The number of beneficiary entities/persons that have this protocol is increased (GOBCAN GEP)
- Number of training pills disseminated aimed at gender awareness (GOBCAN GEP)
- Percentage of reviewed publications that do not contain inclusive language (GOBCAN GEP)
- Number of performances in tribute to scientific women (GOBCAN GEP)
- Number of mini-fairs held on women and girls in science (GOBCAN GEP)
- Number of actions in which compliance with inclusive and non-sexist communication and advertising is verified (GOBCAN GEP)

³⁸ Gender Equality Plans of Athena Partners 2022

4. Guidelines and timetable

Starting from the discussion within the previous sections of this deliverable, and considering also the experiences of previous projects ([R&I PEERS](#), [Gender Balance for Innovation](#)) (...) *Monitoring involves periodical understanding of the level of institutionalization of Gender Equality in each Organisation (monitoring the state) and the implementation of the GEPs processes (i.e. its actions).*

The ATHENA project will follow a monitoring strategy based on:

- 1) the GEP that each organisation has identified within WP4;
- 2) the framework of indicators identified by each organisation in relation to each GEP.

The monitoring strategy has been defined, and it consists of four steps (see Figure 1):

- 1) Customising the GEPs, identifying targets and periodicity for each indicator.
- 2) Collecting objective data from the organisations submitted periodically (state data).
- 3) Collecting data on the actions carried out within the GEPs from each organization involved in the project (process data).
- 4) Analysis of all data collected.

Figure 2. Athena Project Monitoring process

The implementation of the M&E system of GEPs within Athena Project the detailed activities within the M&E system are foreseen (see Table 6.).

Table 6. Athena Monitoring & Evaluation Process	
Action	Period/Deadline
Customising the GEPs, identifying targets and periodicity for each indicator	M15 (15 June 2022)
Collecting data (state + process data)	M15 - M24
Analysis of all data collected, Monitoring Report 1 Customising the GEPs, making corrections	M24 (31 January 2023)
Collecting data (state + process data)	M25 - M36
Analysis of all data collected, Monitoring Report 2 Customising the GEPs, making corrections	M36 (31 January 2024)
Collecting data (state + process data)	M25 - M236
Satisfaction Survey	M35 (30 December 2024)
Analysis of all data collected, Monitoring & Evaluation Report	M36 (31 January 2025)

References

1. A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2020%3A152%3AFIN>
2. EC, DG Budget 2005, Evaluation EU Activities, , <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/6ff3c67d-bd1e-4909-8158-01cd57c4375d>
3. EIGE 2021, Gender equality and the socio-economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, <https://eige.europa.eu/publications/gender-equality-and-socio-economic-impact-covid-19-pandemic>
4. EIGE
5. [Gender Equality in Academia and Research - GEAR Tool](#)
6. [GENERA - Gender Equality Network in the European Research Area](#)
7. [Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans](#)
8. [R&I PEERS, Gender Balance for Innovation](#)
9. [RESPECTWomen: Preventing violence against women](#)

Annex I. Athena GEP Logic Model Matrix – template for defining outputs and outcomes indicators

Area in the EU GEP Guidance	Objectives/Goals/Challenges	Action within the GEP in Athena	Description of the action	Indicators	Thresholds	Direct target	Person in Charge, her role within the Organisation:	Time frame	Outcomes/results	Remarks/Obstacle
Work-life balance and organisational culture	<i>Objective 1.1.: Identify the objective(s)/ goals – your “vision of change” in the area. This should be the basis for choosing appropriate gender indicators against which to track progress.</i>	<i>Define activity(ies) relating to the specific objective.</i>	<i>Describe in short the action: what kind of work/tasks you are planning to do within the activity.</i>	<i>What are the key indicators related to the action? Provide implementation-oriented indicators, e.g. number of seminars, participants, documents, provided procedures, etc.</i>	Unsatisfactory: < Satisfactory: = Very satisfactory: >	<i>to whom the action is addressed and is intended to have an impact, eg. students, academic staff, non academic staff etc.</i>	<i>Provide information who will be responsible for implementation of the task.</i>	<i>Provide period/ date</i>	<i>Define the expected results regarding to the objective. Try to define gender indicators to assess the outcomes and impacts of gender mainstreaming in Your Institution. Consider a combination of qualitative and quantitative indicators to generate richer data.</i>	
		<i>Action 1.1.2.</i>								
Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	<i>Objective 2.1.</i>	<i>Action 2.1.1.</i>								
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	<i>Objective 3.1.</i>	<i>Action 3.1.1.</i>								
Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	<i>Objective 4.1.</i>	<i>Action 4.1.1.</i>								
Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment	<i>Objective 5.1.</i>	<i>Action 5.1.1.</i>								